

Supplementary material for
**Assesing Spherical Harmonics Interpolation of
Time-Aligned Head-Related Transfer Functions**

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1 Physical Evaluation - Additional Figures

Figure S1: Standard deviation of the group delay across all source positions after and before the alignment (UP) for all tested methods.

Figure S2: Reference and interpolated HRTFs for a source at $\Omega = (90^\circ, 0^\circ)$, selected SH orders N , and interpolation methods UP and OBTA.

Figure S3: Reference and interpolated HRTFs for a source at $\Omega = (90^\circ, 0^\circ)$, selected SH orders N , and interpolation methods FDTA and PC.

Figure S4: Reference and interpolated HRTFs for a source at $\Omega = (90^\circ, 0^\circ)$, selected SH orders N , and interpolation method SUpDEq.

Figure S5: Left ear energetic error ΔG vs. SH order averaged across frequency and source position on the entire sphere as well as in the ipsilateral and contralateral region.

Figure S6: Left ear energetic error $\Delta G(\Omega)$ averaged across frequencies for all interpolation methods and SH orders $N = \{1, 2, 3\}$.

Figure S7: Left ear energetic error $\Delta G(\Omega)$ averaged across frequencies for all interpolation methods and SH orders $N = \{4, 5, 6\}$.

Figure S8: Left ear energetic error $\Delta G(\Omega)$ averaged across frequencies for all interpolation methods and SH orders $N = \{7, 8, 9\}$.

Figure S9: Left ear energetic error $\Delta G(\Omega)$ averaged across frequencies for all interpolation methods and SH orders $N = \{10, 11, 12\}$.

Figure S10: Left ear energetic error $\Delta G(\Omega)$ averaged across frequencies for all interpolation methods and SH orders $N = \{13, 14, 15\}$.

2 Perceptual Evaluation - Additional Figure

Figure S11: Histograms of the estimated PSEs for all tested conditions with normal distribution fit. The optimal width and number of the bins for each histogram was calculated according to the Freedman–Diaconis rule. Histograms highlighted in green show a normal distribution according to a Shapiro-Wilk test with Hochberg-correction for multiple hypothesis testing. Histograms highlighted in red show a non-normal distribution as indicated by the Shapiro-Wilk test, which in this case occurred for only one of the 12 tested conditions, caused by a single data point.

3 Perceptual Evaluation - Static Binaural Renderings

As part of the supplementary material, we provide a zip file containing static binaural renderings in the form of *.wav files for all tested conditions. The different stimuli can be easily compared using the pure data patch (see Fig. S12), which is part of the zip folder. To run the pure data patch, please download the newest release of *purr data* from here: <https://github.com/agraef/purr-data/releases>. Please also see the *readme.txt* file in the zip folder for further information.

Figure S12: Graphical user interface of the pure data patch provided to compare the different static stimuli.